

THE STRUCTURE OF THE CONCEPT “HOME” AND ITS METHOD OF RESEARCH

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The notion of the concept began to form and is widely used in linguistic studies since the mid XX century. One of the first linguists, who have studied the concept, was Askoldov C.A. In his article “The concept and the word” published in 1928, the researcher treats the concept as a “mental entity that replaces us in the process of thought vague set of objects of the same kind of”¹.

The identification of the terms of the concept and the concept is illustrated by the Grand-agency encyclopedia Dictionary of linguistics: “The concept (concept) - the phenomenon of the same order as the meaning of the word, but is not considered a somewhat different system of linkages, value - in the language system, the concept - a system of logical relations and forms, as studied in linguistics, and a logic”.

This definition supports the idea that the concept of nature in terms of new approaches to language learning is different from the meaning of the word and is interdisciplinary in nature, and this, in turn, serves as one of the main provisions contemporary linguistic research. In this regard, the concept has a broader meaning than the concept, and established as an independent and a key term in the studies on the problems of cognitive linguistics, cultural linguistics, psycholinguistics, philosophy of language, communicative linguistics, pragmatic linguistics, i.e., all the linguistic areas, based on the interdisciplinary nature of language learning.

However, the identification of the concept and the concept is not excluded, as some scholars consider these terms as synonyms.

The term “concept” is traced back to 1554–60 (Latin *conceptum* – “something conceived”) but what is today termed “the Cognitive linguistics, is the process of producing and transforming concepts (meanings), so the most important object of research in cognitive linguistics is a concept. Concepts, speaking as components of our consciousness and our knowledge of the world are studied in philosophy, psychology, cognitive linguistics, cultural linguistics and other humanities. Exploring the nature of the concept in cognitive linguistics is paramount. Any attempt to understand the nature of the concept leads to awareness of the existence of a number of related concepts and terms. First of all, this is a concept, a notion and meaning.

Firstly, a concept (abstract term: conception) is a cognitive unit of meaning an abstract idea or a mental symbol sometimes defined as a “unit of knowledge,” built from other units which act as a concept's characteristics. A concept is typically associated with a corresponding representation in a language or symbology such as a single meaning of a term. There are prevailing theories in contemporary philosophy which attempt to explain the nature of concepts. The representational theory of mind proposes that concepts are mental representations, while the semantic theory of concepts (originating with Frege's distinction between concept and object) holds that they are abstract objects. Ideas are taken to be concepts, although abstract concepts do not necessarily appear to the mind as images as some ideas do.

¹S.A.Askol’dov. “Sketch of a History of the Ideal and the Real” - Praga, 1969.p 53.

Many philosophers consider concepts to be a fundamental ontological category of being. The meaning of “concept” is explored in mainstream information science, cognitive science, metaphysics, and philosophy of mind.

In cognitive linguistics, abstract concepts are transformations of concrete concepts derived from embodied experience. The mechanism of transformation is structural mapping, in which properties of two or more source domains are selectively mapped onto a blended space.²

The development of methods for studying the concept is today one of the topical problems of modern linguistics. American linguists define concept as a unit of thinking.³ Conceived as a complex education and consciousness unit, representing the linguistic means and forms a semantic space of language, which is studied by means of specially developed methods in linguistics. Research concepts aimed at “interpretation of the meaning structures, objectifying certain features of concepts; to identify the frequency (typical of many concepts) taxonomic characteristics and the definition of the characteristics common to these typological traits studied concepts. Then - based on them - a generalization of the concepts of features, as well as the selection of conceptual structures and cognitive models of language schemes actualization concepts studied in compared languages”.

Currently, the development of methods of conceptual analysis involves the study of the interaction of human cognition with linguistic structures, has accumulated some experience. This issue has received considerable attention in the work of linguists such as N.D. Arutyunova, E.S. Kubryakova, S. Stepanov, R.M. Frumkin, M.V. Pimenov, Z.D. Popova, I.A. Sternin, V.I. Karasik. The origins of conceptual analysis are incorporated in the frame of the theory proposed by M. Minsky. The method is based on the position that the human perception of reality is carried out by comparing its existing frames in the memory, the data structures associated with the conceptual objects that are stored in the memory and are necessary to represent a stereotyped situation. Under the frame is defined as “a unit of knowledge organized around some concepts, but in contrast to associations containing the data on the material, typical and possible for this concept,” differing conventional nature, they concretize, which is typical of a certain culture.

The most complete description of the method of conceptual analysis obtained in Z.D. Popova, I.A. Sternin, which marked the main stages of the analysis of the concept, based on the semantic-cognitive method. According to this procedure, the concept analysis is carried out as follows: 1) describes the macrostructure of the concept, ie, It is the distribution of cognitive symptoms in the figurative, information components and interpretive field and establish their relationship on brightness / predominance in the structure of the concept; 2) describes the concept of categorical structure, ie, It is “the identification of the hierarchy of cognitive classifications, conceptualizes corresponding object or phenomenon, and a description of the concept of a hierarchy of cognitive classifications”; 3) describes the field organization identified cognitive symptoms, ie, set core proximal and extreme periphery on the basis of cognitive signs and symptoms of cognitive content is represented as a field structure.

It should be noted that our proposed integrated, incremental analysis we conduct based on several principles:

²Fauconnier, Gilles and Mark Turner “ [The Way We Think](#).”-New York: Basic Books, 2006.-25-p.

³Lakoff, George and Johnson, Mark.“Philosophy in the Flesh.The Embodied Mind and its Challenge to Western Thought.” NewYork: BasicBooks, 2007.-87-p.

- a) structural principle, involving cognitive signs distribution conceptual, imaginative and valuable components;
- b) the principle of the field, which helps to establish the hierarchy of cognitive-conceptual signs related to the core or the periphery of the structure of the concept;
- c) cross-layer principle, involving consideration of linguistic resources, verbalized this concept at the level of vocabulary, word formation, phraseology units paremeological, aphoristic, artistic, journalistic and sacred texts;
- g) comparison / comparison of the principle of contributing to the establishment and allomorphic isomorphic cognitive-conceptual features of the concept under consideration in order to identify its cultural identity.

The test procedure involves several stages:

- Revealed a set of linguistic resources on the lexical level, word formation, phraseology, paremiological units, aphoristic, artistic, journalistic and sacred texts, the study verbalized concept in each of the languages in question;
- Set a hierarchical system of cognitive-conceptual signs by constructing cognitive maps based on the lexicographical definitions of associative connections, encyclopedic knowledge structures, philosophical, cultural character of each of the above levels of verbalization of the concept under study;
- Carried out the interpretation of the cognitive-conceptual signs on a) field-principle; ascribed to the core or periphery at every level of verbalization of the concept; b) structural principle; belonging to the conceptual, figurative and value components of the concept of structure;
- Analyzes the conceptual signs based on lexicographical interpretation keyword-representatives their word formation and phraseological bonds which, depending on the level in question constitute the core or the periphery of the structure of the concept;
- Identifies the cognitive-conceptual signs based on metaphorical nominations forming shaped component of the concept of structure at every level of verbalization of the concept under study;
- An analysis of the value component of the concept of the structure reveals the cognitive-conceptual signs that determine the importance of the concept being studied for the carriers studied linguocultures. The analysis is performed at each level of verbalization Home / Uy;
- Held an interlayer, comparative and cross-cultural analysis of linguistic units of English, Uzbek and Russian languages that represent the analyzed concept. The purpose of this analysis is to identify the cultural identity cognitive and conceptual features of the concept of structure in each of the languages in question;
- Set the interaction concept Home / Uy with other concepts that make up the conceptual sphere of the test concept are identified and interpreted them correlative cognitive-conceptual signs to facilitate the identification of conceptual space throughout concept spheres;
- Identifies the cognitive-conceptual signs, forming a religious picture of the world in each of the considered linguocultures.

To sum up, this paragraph of the work is based on the linguistic perception of concept. It differs from other views, because concept is related to a certain way of its expression in language. Concept is an ideal content, any thinking unit, having the meaning, a complex thinking image, operational thinking unit verbalized by different means of speech in the process of communication.

References:

1. Azamat Ziyov. O'zbek davlatchiligi tarixi. -T.; Sharq, 2000.-366 b.
2. Chilton, P.A. Nukespeak: Nuclear Language, Culture and Propaganda
P.A. Chilton // Nukespeak: The Media and the Bomb / ed. by C. Aubrey. - L.: Comedia Publishing Group, 1982. - pp. 94-112.
3. Cicero. (1971) Selected Works, trans. M. Grant. Harmondsworth: Penguin.
4. Cobb, R. The Political Uses of Symbolism / R. Cobb, Ch.Elder // American Politics Quarterly. - 1973. - Vol. 1, № 3. - pp. 305-338.
5. Diamond, P. (1995) Status and Power in Verbal Interaction: A Study of Discourse in a Close-knit Social Network. Amsterdam: Benjamins.
6. Gasking, D (1960) Clusters. Australasian Journal of Philosophy 38 (1):1-36.